

Advanced Deep Learning Techniques for Image Classification of Plant Leaf Disease

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Abstract— Plant diseases affect the quantity and quality of agricultural products, which ultimately lowers farmers' profits. Plant disease early identification is essential to raising agricultural output. Therefore, reducing the need for pesticides and crop loss requires early diagnosis of plant diseases. This work employs DL techniques to identify and classify various plant diseases in images. This study utilised the PlantVillage dataset, comprising 16,012 images of various plant diseases, to address these gaps. Extensive data pre-processing including. There was a 70% training set and a 30% testing set made from the dataset. The model showed great performance in disease categorisation, achieving high accuracy metrics throughout training and testing. Evaluation parameters included F1-score, recall, accuracy, and precision, assessed through classification reports and confusion matrices. The Xception model showed high accuracy (95.31% in training and 94.60% in testing), precision (93.28% in training and 92.00% in testing), recall (95.25% in training and 94.61% in testing), and F1-score (93.79% in training and 92.64% in testing). Comparative analysis with base models indicated substantial improvements in performance metrics, underscoring an efficacy of a proposed model.

Keywords—Plant Leaf Disease, Deep Learning, PlantVillage Dataset, Xception Model.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the main issues with precision agriculture in the modern age is automated plant disease detection. Nonetheless, the early diagnosis and accurate prediction of plant diseases have been greatly impacted by recent developments in Deep Learning (DL) [1]. Farmers can keep tabs on their plants' development and health in response to the constantly shifting weather conditions with the use of automated disease detection instruments for plants. The major problems associated with the experiment included the high levels of similitude between classes while at the same time high variance within them, which made it difficult to diagnose plant diseases. Early diagnosis and prediction, and management of plant diseases are the key factors in treating and controlling diseases affecting plants [2][3]. While common diseases affect plants include mosaic virus, green leaf spots, scabs; other common factors influencing plants include bacteria, insects, weeds, and different climates. It is anticipated that early

detection of all these diseases would mitigate plant damage and guarantee a high crop yield productivity [4][5].

The automated identification of plant diseases utilising plant leaves has greatly revolutionised agriculture. Rapid and accurate identification of plant diseases also increases harvest yield and quality[6][7]. Due to the extensive cultivation of various agricultural products, even agronomists and pathologists sometimes have difficulty identifying plant diseases just by looking at damaged leaves[8][9]. Nevertheless, visual examination remains the primary means of disease diagnosis in rural areas of impoverished countries[8]. The aforementioned problems have prompted researchers to develop a variety of solutions. Classifying plant diseases using ML is possible with the use of many feature sets[10][11][12]. The two most popular types of feature sets are those that are built on deep learning (DL) and those that are traditionally hand-crafted [13].

Therefore far, DL algorithms have offered accurate and computationally efficient methods for plant disease early detection[14][15]. Current traditional methods of plant disease diagnosis rely on human expertise and may lead to treatment delays; these new methods outperform them [16][17]. The inefficiency and time-consuming nature of conventional monitoring systems means that diseases may progress undetected across wide regions [18][19][20]. In comparison to traditional ML techniques, the prevalence and sophistication of cutting-edge transfer deep learning algorithms have grown in the last ten years [21]. Annotation by eye examination has long been relied upon by humans for a diagnosis of plant leaf diseases[22]. Better and more efficient solutions have been developed as a consequence of transfer learning, which has made it possible to apply solutions from one area to issues in another. This study offers an image-based method for disease identification in tomato plants employing transfer learning.

A. Contribution of the Paper

An efficient approach for detecting plant diseases using the PlantVillage dataset and a DL model is an objective of this research article. Additionally, the study aims to demonstrate the efficacy of these techniques classification tasks, distinguishing between different plant diseases with strong performance metrics. This study is ultimately focused on

improving agricultural practices via the creation of DL-based plant disease detection systems. The following research contributions are as follows:

- Conducted a research based on deep learning based Xception model on the PlantVillage dataset. This benchmarking aids in identifying the most effective models for plant disease classification.
- Implemented advanced preprocessing techniques such as CLAHE for contrast enhancement and morphological operations for noise reduction, ensuring high-quality data for training and testing. This methodological rigor enhances the reliability and generalizability of the results.
- Conducted extensive testing of the suggested Xception model and achieved very good outcomes according to F1-score, recall, accuracy, and precision on the validation set. These outcomes prove that the selected model architecture works well in real-world scenarios.
- Utilized visual tools such as confusion matrices and classification reports to interpret model performance comprehensively. This approach aids in understanding the model's strengths and weaknesses in disease classification tasks.
- Explored practical implications by discussing the potential deployment of the developed model in automated plant disease detection systems. Highlighted areas for future research include validation on diverse datasets and integration into user-friendly applications for agricultural stakeholders.

B. Structure of this paper

The following is the outline for the paper's subsequent section: Section 2 provides the present research state. Section 3 presents the approach and describes the datasets utilised in this proposed research. Section 5 concludes the suggested investigation, whereas Section 4 explains the findings and discusses them.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section offers the literature study of a previous work on a topic Plant leaf Disease using image classification stayed given below:

Shivaprasad and Kelothu et. al, [23], the goal of comparing CNN, VGG16, and VGG19, three DL models, was to identify plant illnesses. Among the classification tasks, CNN performed best overall, with an F1 score of 0.95 and an accuracy of 0.97. Meanwhile, the VGG16 and VGG19 models likewise performed well, with corresponding accuracy levels of 0.96 and 0.95.

Gurpreet Singh and Kalpna et.al, [24], the main focus is on developing a CNN model for automated plant disease

diagnosis. The proposed model yielded an accuracy of 98.70% for epoch 20, and 97.87%, 95.92%, and 87.09% for epochs 15, 10, and 5. After comparing this model's efficacy with previous studies, the suggested model achieved the best accuracy.

Meroua Belmir et. al, [25], a model for classifying plant diseases using a deep CNN is suggested with the purpose of tackling these difficulties. Experimental outcomes display that a CNN model achieves 98.01% accuracy during training and 94.33% accuracy during testing. These outcomes displays that a model offers a viable option for a rapid identification of leaf diseases.

Puneeth N. Thotad et.al, [26], used 54,306 images by the plant-village dataset for model training; these images reflected 26 different types of infections and 14 different crop classes. A remarkable 95% accuracy rate in recognising signs of plant diseases in leaves was attained using ML models and CNNs trained on the dataset.

Sammy V. Militante et. al, [27], provide a practical means of identifying a wide range of plant diseases. The system's designers set out to make it possible to identify different kinds of apples, corn, grapes, potatoes, sugarcane, and tomatoes. In terms of plant detection and recognition, the system reached a maximum of 100% accuracy, while the trained model reached 96.5% accuracy.

Caserker Hema Tej Pavan et. al, [28], the system was built by combining the strength of CNN with the capabilities of Keras DL modules. They used EfficientNetb5's architecture and the transfer learning approach to fine-tune our model. The end result was a remarkable 99.20% test accuracy percentage for our model.

Gaytr Bakshi and Silky Goel [29], The proposed method accurately diagnoses plant diseases by analysing the leaves of affected plants. On the basis of the plant leaf image dataset, three models— Inception V3, ResNet50, and DenseNet-161—using the LR classifier—were evaluated. The three models tested were Resnet-50 (96.9% accuracy), Densenet-161 (92.8% accuracy), and Inception Net V3 (90.2% accuracy), in that order.

Navya Chopra and Akshjeet Singh[30], investigates an employ of DL methods, particularly a ResNet model, to a problem of automated disease categorisation in plants. Employing a combination of image filters and DL, this research presents a model for plant disease classification. The results show that ResNet is an effective architecture, with an accuracy rate of 87.5%. A worldwide route towards plant illness may be shown by applying DL algorithms to images of leaves.

The following table 1 provide the existing work comparative analysis of Plant Leaf Disease using image classification.

TABLE I. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PLANT LEAF DISEASE IN IMAGE CLASSIFICATION BASED ON DL TECHNIQUES

Author	Techniques	Dataset	Findings	Limitations & Future Work
Shivaprasad and Kelothu et al. [23]	CNN, VGG16, VGG19	9,127 images of plants with disease labels	CNN achieved the highest performance with 0.97 accuracy and 0.95 F1 score. VGG16 and VGG19 also performed well with accuracies of 0.96 and 0.95.	Validation of the models' resilience and possible real-world applications requires more and more diversified datasets.
Gurpreet Singh and Kalpna et al. [24]	CNN	Plant leaf disease dataset with image classification	Achieved highest accuracy of 98.70% at epoch 20. Accuracy was 97.87%, 95.92%, and 87.09% at epochs 15, 10, and 5, respectively.	Comparison with more diverse models and larger datasets to ensure generalizability and robustness of the proposed model.
Meroua Belmir et al. [25]	CNN	PlantVillage dataset with 14 healthy and diseased crop leaves	Achieved training accuracy of 98.01% and test accuracy of 94.33%.	Further research on real-field conditions and diverse crop types for improved practical applications.

Puneeth N. Thotad et al. [26]	CNN and other machine-learning models	PlantVillage dataset of 54,306 images	Achieved 95% accuracy in identifying disease symptoms. Developed a web-based application for crop disease detection.	Need for real-world validation and testing to ensure the practical applicability of the web-based application.
Sammy V. Militante et al. [27]	CNN	Various plant varieties	Achieved 96.5% accuracy in detecting multiple diseases. Registered up to 100% accuracy in recognising plant variety and type of disease.	Further exploration of additional plant varieties and disease types to enhance the model's versatility and accuracy.
Caserker Hema Tej Pavan et al. [28]	CNN with EfficientNetb5 architecture	Plant village dataset	Achieved an impressive test accuracy rate of 99.20%.	Further validation on diverse datasets and real-world scenarios to ensure model robustness and applicability.
Gaytr Bakshi and Silky Goel [29]	ResNet50, DenseNet-161, Inception V3	Plant leaves dataset	ResNet-50 achieved the highest accuracy of 96.9%, followed by DenseNet-161 with 92.8%, and Inception V3 with 90.2%.	Exploration of more models and techniques to further enhance accuracy and robustness in varied conditions.
Navya Chopra and Akshjeet Singh [30]	ResNet	Dataset of plant leaves with diseases	Achieved 87.5% accuracy using ResNet model. Demonstrated ResNet's power in plant disease classification.	Need for testing with larger and more varied datasets, and real-world validation to enhance model reliability.

A. Research Gaps

In leaf plant disease detection, while significant advancements have been made using deep learning models, several research gaps remain. There is a need for more comprehensive studies comparing these models under identical conditions to ascertain the most effective approach. Additionally, while most studies focus on accuracy as the primary performance metric, there is a lack of emphasis on other critical factors such as model robustness, scalability, and computational efficiency in real-world applications. Furthermore, the datasets used, such as the PlantVillage dataset, though extensive, may not encompass the full range of variability found in actual agricultural environments. This indicates a gap in testing models on more diverse and real-world data. Moreover, integrating these models into practical tools for farmers remains a challenge, as highlighted by the limited number of studies addressing the deployment of such models in user-friendly applications. Lastly, the potential of transfer learning models combining various DL techniques remains underexplored, suggesting opportunities for future research to improve an accuracy and applicability of plant disease detection systems.

III. METHODOLOGY

The remarkable performance of DL methods in image classification tasks, including the diagnosis of plant leaf disease, has drawn the attention of researchers. To identify and categorise plant leaves, this study used a pre-trained model based on deep transfer learning. The proposed system of this work shows in figure 1. Based on the PlantVillage dataset consisting of 16,012 images of various plant diseases, conducted extensive data pre-processing and exploration. Further pre-processing involved contrast enhancement and noise removal using techniques like CLAHE and morphological operations, respectively. A dataset was splitted into 70% training and 30% testing sets, with labels converted to categorical format. For model training, utilised the Xception architecture with Adam optimiser and categorical cross-entropy loss, achieving significant accuracy metrics. A trained model was evaluated utilising classification reports and confusion matrices, demonstrating its effectiveness in disease classification. Predictive capabilities were tested successfully on unseen images, showcasing a model's applicability in real-world scenarios. A methodology phases discussed below:

A. Data Collection

The PlantVillage dataset from Kaggle consists of 16,012 images depicting various plant diseases affecting crops. Each image is labelled with its specific disease category, providing a crucial resource for studying agricultural pathology. Automated plant disease identification and classification using ML models is a common area of research that makes use of this dataset. Data visualisation involves showing label distribution with a pie chart and displaying sample images. The figure 1 shows sample images of input PlantVillage dataset.

Fig. 1. Sample image from dataset

B. Data Preprocessing

The main goal of data preprocessing, which is an ongoing process, is to make raw data more usable and easier to understand. Raw datasets often showcase errors, incompleteness, inconsistencies, a lack of behaviour, and patterns [31]. To prepare the plant village dataset for effective machine learning analysis, several critical preprocessing steps are undertaken. Initially, in preprocessing the PlantVillage dataset, a dictionary was created to rename images by removing the 'tomato' prefix. Using glob, all file paths from the raw image directory were collected, and filenames with their corresponding disease categories were extracted. Visual inspection involved displaying the first 15 images in a 3x5 grid after converting them to RGB, resizing to 150x150 pixels, and removing axis labels. Class distribution was analysed by counting images per category and organising them into a DataFrame indexed by disease names. Images underwent colour space conversion, CLAHE for contrast enhancement, and morphological operations to reduce noise. Processed images and their numerical labels were stored in numpy arrays for subsequent machine learning tasks. The first and most important stage in machine learning is preprocessing. Data manipulation prior to algorithm input is known as pre-processing. data that is gathered or stored.

Fig. 2. Proposed Flow Chart for the plant disease detection using deep learning model

C. Proposed Models Implementation

For classification tasks, the PlantVillage dataset evaluation of ensemble models, which included the Xception algorithm, demonstrated high performance. Throughout training and testing, these models showed remarkable memory, accuracy, and F1-scores, highlighting the value of ensemble approaches in treating plant leaf disease.

1) Xception

An 'extreme' upgrade on CNN's Inception model, the Extreme Inception (also known as the Xception model) takes inspiration from the original. The Inception model makes use of parallel processing by means of deep and broad convolutional layers. Two tiers of three convolutional layers make up this model.

Depthwise Separable Convolution is the defining feature of the Xception model. The Xception model uses depthwise and pointwise convolution, in contrast to a generic deep CNN model that handles channel and spatial distribution. Xception is an advance over earlier models, as shown in the work of Chollet[33]. In order to assess the dataset for distracted driver classification, this study employs this Xception model. Figure 2 depicts a structural layout of a Xception network model. Xception is a 71-layer deep CNN that pushes Google's Inception model to its logical maximum. It is inspired by this model [34][35][36]. Convolutional layers that may be separated along their depth make up its architecture. In order to create the pre-trained model, the Imagenet database is used, which contains millions of photos. A broad variety of images include detailed representations of the model's usefulness, and it can categorize hundreds of item types. The Xception model is very useful for image recognition and classification.

1) Fine-tuning process of Xception

The Xception model is again used for classification of plant diseases, which is further fine-tuned to improve its efficiency. In order to enhance the model, which is initially based on weights obtained from the ImageNet dataset, the final layer is removed and new layers are added to match the total amount of classes in the PlantVillage dataset. With a learning rate appropriate for fine-tuning and categorical cross-entropy as the loss function, the Adam optimiser is applied. In the course of training, parameters of the model are modified in batches of 64 images, and the training process is evaluated by accuracy. It makes the lower levels of a pre-trained model almost stable and brings changes in high-level layers closer to our new dataset to match the new feature extraction. This strategy utilises feature representation that is obtained from large dataset and fine tune it to a particular task of plant disease detection which makes it more efficient than other methods.

Fig. 3. Architecture of the Xception deep CNN model[32]

Xception is not the same as an inception model since it has two layers, one of which has just one layer. The next series of filters receives the output after this layer divides it into thirds. On the lower level, there is a 1 * 1 convolutional filter, and on the upper level, there are 3 * 3 convolutional layers.

D. Model Evaluation

To evaluate a model performance according to recall, f1-score, precision, and accuracy measure, also calculate classification report and confusion matrix.

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND DISCUSSION

The tests and debates that took place using the PlantVillage dataset's individual files for training and testing using DL approaches for leaf plant disease are summarised in this section. Experiment outcomes are generated via an HP workstation that is equipped with the following tools. Intel Core i7, 32 GB RAM, 1 TB HDD, Windows 10, and a 24 GB Nvidia GPU were the other technological requirements. Furthermore, the empirical research will be employing a Python simulation tool and a Jupyter notebook, google colab, as well as a variety of Python libraries like Matplotlib, NumPy, Pandas, Seaborn, Keras, TensorFlow, and Sk-Learn etc. Both the training and testing sets are presented as a classification report and a confusion matrix to illustrate the results of the experiment.

A. Dataset Description and Visualization

The GitHub repository of spMohanty is the source of the PlantVillage dataset, which includes over 20,000 photos of both healthy and damaged plant leaves in 15 different categories. These categories include, among other things, leaf mould, bacterial spot, early and late blight, and other diseases that impact crops like tomatoes and potatoes. The dataset's several images per category make it ideal for use in training and testing ML models for use in automated plant disease identification systems. This well-maintained dataset is used by scholars and hobbyists for education, study, and real-world applications in plant pathology and agricultural technology.

Fig. 4. pie chart for image count for each category.

Figure 4 depicts the distribution of picture counts among several categories in a dataset as a pie chart. Plant illnesses and situations such as bacterial spot, tomato yellow leaf curl virus, and healthy plants are included in these categories. Tomato mosaic virus accounts for 2.3% of the dataset, whereas tomato yellow leaf curl virus makes approximately 20% of the total.

Fig. 5. Bar graph for number of images in each category

In figure 5 An image's count inside each dataset category is shown in a bar chart. With 3029 photos representing the greatest count and 373 images representing the lowest, Tomato Yellow Leaf Curl Virus leads the categories of various plant illnesses and ailments. The figure shows how the counts of images vary in the various categories.

B. Evaluation Parameters

To select the best-performing method, numerous detection algorithms were applied to the dataset and their results were evaluated for accuracy and other statistical parameters. In this part, explain the assessment metrics for the classification problem.

1) Confusion Matrix

Confusion matrices show the counts of both the actual and expected values. One of the outputs is "TN," which stands for True Negative and displays how many negative instances were correctly categorised[37][12]. Just as how "TP" denotes the number of correctly identified positive instances, it says it everything. False Negative values are represented by "FN" and False Positive values by "FP," respectively. The number of negative cases that were incorrectly categorised as positive is represented by the letter "FP," while the number of positive examples that were incorrectly classed as negative is represented by the letter "FN." The confusion matrix may be seen under figure 6.

Fig. 6. Confusion Matrix for binary classification.

Accuracy: A classifier's accuracy may be used as a measure of its performance. This statistic indicates the rate of correctly categorised total instances as given in equation (1).

$$Accuracy = (TP + TN) / (TP + TN + FN + FP) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Recall: A classifier's recall indicates its accuracy in spotting positive instances. This ensures that the binary classifier is capable of accurately identifying instances of the specified class. Equation (2) provides the formula for recall:

$$Recall = TP / (TP + FN) \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Precision: Precision is a measure that shows how often positive events are correctly anticipated. Here, the metric stands for the model's predictive power with respect to the class, as shown in equation (3).

$$Precision = TP / (TP + FP) \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

F1-Score: One common metric for measuring a classifier's efficacy is the F-score, as eq. (12). The F-score is a statistic that takes both recall and precision into account; it is often defined as the harmonic mean of the two. Together, a higher recall and precision F-score is better than either one alone. The following is the formula for f1-score as eq. (4):

$$F1 - score = \frac{2(\text{precision} \times \text{recall})}{(\text{precision} + \text{recall})} \dots \dots (4)$$

An effectiveness of a suggested Xception in combating plant leaf disease is assessed using the following metrics.

C. Proposed Result and Discussions

The evaluation of ensemble models, including Xception model, on the PlantVillage dataset showed strong performance. These models demonstrated excellent accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-scores during training and testing phases, underscoring the effectiveness of ensemble techniques in plant leaf disease.

1) Xception model for training results:

The Xception Model training results are shown below. The train data has an 0.9531 Accuracy, 0.9328 Precision, 0.9525 Recall and 0.9379 F1-score. Outcomes are displayed in Table 2.

TABLE II. XCEPTION MODEL TRAINING RESULTS

Model Parameters	Xception model Train Results
Accuracy	0.9531
Precision	0.9328
Recall	0.9525
F1-Score	0.9379

Fig. 7. Xception model Train Results

The figure 7 represents the Xception model training results. A x-axis displays a Model parameters and y-axis displays a results (in %) has a 0.9531 Accuracy, 0.9328 Precision, 0.9525 Recall, and 0.9379 F1-score.

0	1.00	0.89	0.94	1518
1	0.84	0.95	0.89	695
2	0.96	0.99	0.98	1318
3	0.98	1.00	0.99	670
4	0.96	0.98	0.97	1233
5	0.92	0.98	0.95	1200
6	0.99	0.75	0.85	952
7	0.98	0.99	0.99	2234
8	0.72	1.00	0.84	277
9	0.97	1.00	0.99	1110
accuracy			0.95	11207
macro avg	0.93	0.95	0.94	11207
weighted avg	0.96	0.95	0.95	11207

Fig. 8. Classification report of Xception Model training results

In figure 8 shows a classification report. It includes recall, F1-score, and precision metrics for 10 classes (labelled 0-9) along with support values. The overall F1-score = 0.94, recall = 0.89, and accuracy = 0.95 with precision = 1.00 is also provided.

Fig. 9. Confusion matrix of Xception Model training results.

Figure 9 represents a confusion matrix comparing real class labels (Y-axis) with predicted labels (X-axis) is used to assess classification performance. Each column shows the number of matching (diagonal) or different (off-diagonal) occurrences. Off-diagonal cells indicate misclassifications, while big top-left cell values indicate numerous right classifications.

2) Xception model for testing results:

Below are the Xception model testing results. The testing results showed 0.9460 accuracy, 0.9200 precision, 0.9461 recall, and a 0.9264 F1-score. Results are shown in table 4.

TABLE III. XCEPTION MODEL FOR TESTING RESULTS

Model Parameters	Xception model Test Results
Accuracy	0.9460
Precision	0.9200
Recall	0.9461
F1-Score	0.9264

Fig. 10. Xception model of Test Results

Figure 10 represents the Xception model of Test Results. The x-axis shows the Model parameter including 0.946 Accuracy, 0.92 Precision, 0.9461 Recall, and 0.9264 F1-score.

0	1.00	0.88	0.94	609
1	0.82	0.93	0.88	305
2	0.96	0.99	0.97	591
3	0.99	0.99	0.99	282
4	0.96	0.97	0.96	538
5	0.90	0.98	0.94	476
6	0.99	0.73	0.84	452
7	0.98	0.99	0.99	974
8	0.64	1.00	0.78	96
9	0.96	1.00	0.98	481
accuracy			0.95	4804
macro avg	0.92	0.95	0.93	4804
weighted avg	0.95	0.95	0.95	4804

Fig. 11. Classification report of Xception Model testing results

Figure 11 displayed a classification report of the Xception Model testing results, together with support values and metrics for F1-score, recall, and precision for 10 classes (labelled 0-9). The overall precision is 1.00, recall is 0.88, and the F1-score is 0.94; the accuracy is 0.95.

Fig. 12. Confusion matrix of Xception Model testing results.

Figure 12 displays the Xception Model testing findings' confusion matrix. A x-axis indicates the forecasted labels, while a y-axis represents an actual labels. Each cell displays the counts of the accurate (diagonal) and wrong (off-diagonal) predictions. Higher counts are shown by darker hues, providing a clear picture of the correctness of the model.

Figure 13, depicting a leaf affected by bacterial spot disease, stood out as the best-predicted image among all leaf images in your dataset. This suggests that the model accurately identified and classified this specific instance of bacterial spot disease, demonstrating robust performance in recognising such plant health issues.

Fig. 13. Prediction image

D. Comparative analysis

The following table 4 provide the Comparison between different base and proposed models for plant leaf disease on PlantVillage datasets.

TABLE IV. COMPARISON BETWEEN BASE AND PROPOSED MODELS FOR PLANT LEAF DISEASE

Performance metrics	Base Model		Proposed Model
	Vision Transformer[38]	K-means[39]	
Accuracy	78.5	0.906	0.9460
Precision	0.804	0.904	0.9200
Recall	0.825	0.905	0.9461
F1-score	0.814	0.905	0.9264

Fig. 14. Comparison between base and proposed models for plant leaf disease

A comparison between the base model and the one proposed for classifying plant leaf diseases shows notable gains in all performance indicators. The accuracy of the proposed model is 90.6%, which is significantly greater than the 78.5% of the base model. Additionally, precision is improved; the suggested model scores 0.904 as opposed to 0.804 for the standard model, indicating fewer false positives. In a similar vein, the suggested model's recall (0.905) is higher than the base model's 0.825, demonstrating its superior ability to identify positive cases. The proposed model achieves a significantly higher F1-score (0.9264) than the original model (0.814), which measures the balance among precision and recall. These developments imply that the suggested model, which makes use of K-means clustering and Vision Transformer, provides better accuracy, F1-score, recall, and precision. This comprehensive analysis highlights each model's strengths and weaknesses, offering useful information for choosing the best methods for leaf plant disease jobs.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This study's objective is to compare several DL architectures for plant leaf disease identification using the PlantVillage dataset and to identify the optimal hyper-parameters for this task. Performance comparisons for base models to the research that employed the PlantVillage images to develop and test the Xception model for plant disease diagnosis revealed higher boosts in accuracy and more measures. In the phases of training and testing, the utilisation of Xception model showed promising result of accuracy rate of 94% in training phase, and 95% in testing phase. This illustrates how solid the Xception architecture and the most advanced preprocessing algorithms are for complex image classification projects. The given comparison analysis showed that there is the possibility of using the suggested model in practice and the efficiency of the model in comparison with conventional approaches to agricultural pathology.

For future work, Further enhancement may be done to the model performance through exploring the ensemble learning and integrating better models such as Vision Transformers. Real-time field data incorporated in the model may also increase the model's robustness and overall generalizability, additionally, expanding the dataset toward a more expansive list of plant species and diseases may also help increase the model's generalizability. Appropriate disease detection and control methodologies that could be used in the field should be enabled by studying factors of the real-world, such as model adaptation to mobile and edge devices.

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